

**ABDULLA ORIPOVNING “SOHIBQIRON” SHE’RIY DRAMMASIDA BOSH QAHRAMON
TASVIRI**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada Abdulla Oripovning “Sohibqiron” she’riy drammasida bosh qahramon tasviri tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: bosh qahramon, tasvir, drama, insonparvarlik, odil.

Hozirgi o‘zbek she’riyatiga yangicha badiiy tafakkur yo‘sinlarini olib kirgan ardoqli o‘zbek shoiri va jamoat arbobi, zamonaviy o‘zbek she’riyatida inson qalbidagi murakkablik va ziddiyatlarni teran, haqqoniy o‘ziga xos betakror kuylagan taniqli ijodkor Abdulla Oripov tomonidan 1996 yilda yozilgan “Sohibqiron” she’riy drammasi Amir Temurning murakkab umr yo‘li haqqoniy bo‘yoqlarda ochib berilganligi bilan alohida o‘ringa ega.

“Sohibqiron” drammasida Amir Temur janglarda emas, balki ko‘proq o‘ylar girdobida aks ettiriladi. Asarda Temurning murakkab tabiati uning Amir Husayn, sulton Boyazid, amirlar, o‘g‘illariga munosabatini ko‘rsatish mobaynida yorqin aks etgan.

Amir Temur tajribali hukmdor va o‘ychil faylasuf sifatida davlatni ushlab turguvchi tayanchlarni: “Mo‘l xazina, yagona shoh, yengilmas lashkar, - deya belgilaydi. Uning jahongirlik tabiati suruvda bitta cho‘pon bo‘lganiday, xalqni ham bir podshoh boshqarishi kerakligi borasidagi qanoatida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Dramada Temurning fuqarolarga munosabati: “Hukmdorlar seva turib fuqarolarni, Umid hamda qo‘rquv ichra saqlashi darkor”, - degan qarashida aks etadi.

Asarda Amir Temurning o‘z dushmanlari gunohlarini ham kechira oladigan shaxs ekani sulton Boyazid, haddidan oshgan kimsani jazosiz qoldirmasligi Amir Husayn, ezgu amalli kishilarni taqdirlashi Hofiz Sheroziy va Qosimbek timsollari orqali ishonarli aks ettirilgan.

Dostonda Boyazidning Amir Temurga yozgan xatidagi haqoratlar uni urushga kirishishga majbur etishi ishonarli tasvirlangan:

Boyazid

Agarda sen biz tomonga kelmasang,
 Temur bilib qo'yki, xotunlaring uch taloq bo'lgay.
 Agar seni yenga olmay chekinsam ortga
 Unda mening xotunlarim bo'lsin uch taloq.

Muallif hech bir musulmon chidashi mumkin bo'lmagan bunday odobsizlikka Temurning jang bilan javob berishi tabiiyligini tarixiy haqiqatga ham mos holda ko'rsatadi.

“Sohibqiron” asari Amir Temur haqidagi quyidagi she'r bilan boshlanadi:

Har qancha fath etsang arziydi, O'zbek
 Balqibsan bir zotning yuksak shonida
 Temurbek yulduzi oltin qoziqdek
 Charaqlar buyuklar kakhashonida...

Misralardan ko'rinadiki, shoir Amir Temurni buyuk ishlarini qanchalar fath etsak shuncha ozligini ta'kidlamoqda.

Keyingi misralarda parda ochiladi hamda Samarqanddagi Temur saroyida Sohibqiron soch oldirayotgan manzara tasvirlanadi.

Temur

Sartaroshga bosh egar, ha, jahongirlar ham,
 Boshqalarga egilishdan asrasin xudo!
 Biroq senga oddiygina bir gapni aytay....
 Har qandayin bandaga ham kerakdir sirdosh,
 Senga kongil ochsam bo'lar.

Ushbu misralardan ayon bo'ladiki, Temur oddiy sartaroshni ham o'ziga teng ko'rib, sirlarini aytish uchun gap boshlamoqda, bundan asar qahramonining o'z mavqeidan qat'iy nazar, hammani teng ko'rishini bilib olish mumkin.

Temur

Sartarohsan, mana senga boshimni egdim
 Biroq, meni avf etgaysan

Tiz bukolmayman..

Sartarosh

Oyog'ingiz shikast topgan muhorabada

Shu boisdan avf etadi sizni qulingiz.

Bosh qahramon sartarosh yonida boshini egishini hamda iloji bo'lsa tiz cho'kishi ham mumkinligini aytadi, Sartarosh ham Temurga hazil qilib, yog'ingiz shikastlanganligi sababdan uni avf etishini ta'kidlaydi.

Keyingi misralarda Amir Temurning qudratli va jahongir sarkarda bo'lishiga qaramay, kuchni qilichda emas, balki adolatda deb bilishi, xalqini adolat bilan boshqarishi hamda "Kuch - adolatda" degan shior bilan yashashi ta'kidlanadi.

Temur

Men she'rimni o'chmas qilib, shamshirga o'ydim

U bitikning mazmuni shul:

"Kuch – adolatda!"

She'riy drama davomida bosh qahramonning lashkarlari, uning dushmani Amir Husaynni qo'llarini bog'lab Sohibqiron huzuriga olib keladilar, Amir Temur esa unga hurmat ko'rsatib, uning qo'llarini bo'shatishni buyuradi. Shoir ushbu sahna orqali bosh qahramonning oliyjanob hamda insonparvarligi, hattoki dushmanlariga ham hurmat ko'rsatadigan ulug' zot bo'lganligini tasvirlaydi. Keyingi sahnalarda Sohibqironning o'g'li Mironshohning xotini Xonzodabegimning Amir Temur huzuriga kelishi tasvirlanadi. Xonzodaning ko'zlari yig'idan shishgani hamda yuzlari zarbdan ko'karganligini ko'rgan Sohibqiron, bularning sababini so'raydi. Xonzoda Mironshohning kechalari ichib kelayotganligini, mast holatda unga musht tushirayotganligini aytib yig'laydi. Shunda Sohibqiron:

Temur

Kechiring, kelin...

Boshim yerga tekkunchalik egilamanu,

Sizdan uzr so'rayman men –

Qaynotangiz!

Amir Temur buyuk sarkarda bo'lishiga qaramay, o'g'lining qilmishi tufayli, kelinidan bosh egib kechirim so'rayapti, bundan bosh qahramonning naqadar oliyhimmat va adolatli ekanligini bilib olishimiz mumkin. Sohibqironning ushbu sahnadagi gaplaridan uning hammani teng ko'zda ko'rishini, o'zi qilmagan ish uchun ham kelinidan kechirim so'ray oladigan odil podshoh va qaynota ekanligini sezish qiyin emas.

Keyingi baytlarda Temurning dushmani Boyazidning asir olinganligi hamda Sohibqiron huzuriga qo'l-oyoqlari bog'langan holda olib kelinganligi tasvirlangan. Ashaddiy dushmanini abgor holda ko'rgan bosh qahramon esa, mamnun bo'lib dushmanining ustidan kulish o'rniga, unga hurmat ko'rsatib, uni qo'l-oyoqlarini ozod etishni buyuradi.

Temur

Evoh, bu ne hol?

Oyoq-qo'lin yeching darhol,

U axir, shoh-ku!

Chumolilar xor qilishsa arslon rutbasin

Buzilgaydir o'rmonning ham qonuniyati.

Asir tushgan Boyazid bunday hurmatdan hayron qolib, dushman tomonidan ko'rsatilayotgan bunday iltifotga zor emasligini ta'kidlaydi, biroq bosh qahramon asir tushgan bo'lsa-da, shohning o'z hurmati borligini ta'kidlaydi, bundan esa Amir Temurning odil davlat rahbari ekanligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Abdulla Oripovning "Sohibqiron" she'riy drammasida Amir Temur janglarda emas, balki ko'proq o'ylar girdobida aks ettiriladi. Drammada Sohibqironning murakkab umr yo'li haqqoniy bo'yoqlarda ochib berilganligi va qahramonning mahoratli sarkarda, odil podshoh, zehnli ota, e'tiborli turmush o'rtoq hamda adolatli qaynota sifatida tasvirlanganligi tarixiy haqiqatga mos keladi hamda asar qiymatini oshiradi.

This article describes the image of imaginary diseases in the stories of Edgar Allan Poe and the reasons for writing about diseases. The allegory and symbolism by depicting the Red Death.¹

¹ Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe's "The Masque of the Red Death". *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.

The article is devoted to the analysis of the *The Magic Hat* book, written by popular Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, from the position of classification elements introduced by the famous Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin.²

The depiction of natural landscapes given in works of art is one of the factors that demonstrate the creative artistic skill.³

В современной методике так же, как и много лет назад, актуальной и нерешенной до сих пор остается проблема поиска и выбора наиболее эффективных и рациональных методов преподавания иностранных языков, соответствующих современным условиям обучения и отвечающих требованиям стандартов современного образования.⁴

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory.⁵

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.⁶

This lesson plan format moves from teachers to centered student. In order to keep this standard lesson plan format from becoming monotonous, it is seminal to memorize that there are a number of variations that can be applied within the various segments of the lesson plan format.⁷

This article deals with the analysis of pastiche in literature, particularly in "The Lightning Thief" by American author Rick Riordan. The research identifies pastiche as a term, which is

² Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN'S THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.

³ Kabilova, F., & Tokhirovna, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.

⁴ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁵ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

⁶ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

⁷ Nodirovna, N. N., & Temirovna, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.

applied to a literary work that is a broad mixture of things-such as themes, concepts, and characters-imitated from different literary works.⁸

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day.¹⁰

В этой статье дается краткий обзор антропонимов, их функций статуса, который они получают от этих, и их специфики.¹¹

The article is about the development of the Soviet era of Uzbek educational dictionary. The educational dictionaries created during this period served mainly to teach Russian in national schools.¹²

This article deals with the description of synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language published in different periods, the systematic description of the similarities and differences between the explanations of synonyms in the publications.¹³

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the right of citizens to vote and to be elected, the foundations of the national electoral system, the basis of which are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and

⁸ Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL "THE LIGHTNING THIEF" BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.

⁹ Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки). *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.

¹⁰ NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

¹¹ Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712

¹² Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.

¹³ Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.

ratification by Uzbekistan, constituting the principles of democracy, including independence, legitimacy, transparency and fairness, enshrined and recognized in other international legal instruments.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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¹⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Toxirjonovich, S. D. (2021). The Institutional Mechanisms Of The Development Of The Electoral System In Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(8), 4378-4384.

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